

Vol:1, Issue: 3 pp: 346-350

JEL Codes: 019,035,Z00

HUA H. (2020). "Research on Dissemination Channels and New Media Integration for
Traditional Folk Dances of Lingnan"

Vol: 1 Issue: 3 pp: 346-350

Keywords: *lingnan dances; traditional folk dances; dissemination channel; new media era; integration*

Article Type Review Article

**Research on Dissemination Channels and New Media Integration for
Traditional Folk Dances of Lingnan**

Arrived Date
16.07.2020

Accepted Date
19.07.2020

Published Date
31.07.2020

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ABSTRACT

In this era of new media, Internet-based short video platforms and interactive video platforms, such as Douyin (Tik Tok in China) and Bilibili, are popular with the post-1990s and post-2000s young generation. Apparently, these new media have changed the ways of dissemination of traditional culture of Lingnan, further extending the channels to spread the traditional folk dances there and speeding up their distribution. The rising short-video social apps and interactive video platforms have diversified the ways of entertainment and revolutionized the old ways of transmission of traditional Lingnan folk dances, fitting traditional culture to the young generation's needs for artistic appreciation and recreational consumption. This paper probes into the various ways of dissemination of the traditional folk dances of Lingnan in this era of Internet-based new media, with a vision to spark up creative thoughts for choreography of Lingnan dances and better adapt traditional Lingnan folk dances to the modern world, thereby facilitating the inheritance and development of the dances.

INTRODUCTION

Lingnan dances, emerging and growing up in the area to the south of the Five Ridges in China, are the various forms of dances typical of the Lingnan area featuring Lingnan-style body language and cultural expressions. These dances showcase the folkways, social customs, cultural heritage and national character of Chinese people in Lingnan, i.e. the area to the south of the Five Ridges in China (Zhou & Su, 2017). Lingnan dances, contemporary or traditional, are one of the most distinctive vibrant manifestations of Lingnan culture. Recent years, the fast-developing mobile Internet technology has provided an unprecedented opportunity for us to disseminate Lingnan dances; new media, emerging at the right time, have extended our ways to spread dances beyond the conventional live shows and radio & TV broadcasts. New media have not only boosted transformation of conventional media like radio and TV, but changed the ways of dissemination of Lingnan dances and other cultural forms. The traditional folk dances of Lingnan, as an indispensable component of Lingnan culture, have rich artistic values. However, few or even no young people can be found to inherit these precious traditional folk dances in this era of new media. It has been a great concern among all walks of life to carry forward this heritage and take advantage of new media to better protect, spread, and unceasingly promote the traditional folk dances of Lingnan.

Dissemination Features of New Media

New media, with short, adaptable and fast massive flows of information, are inclusive, open, diversified and time-sensitive, which are suitable for distribution of traditional folk dances of Lingnan. New media are inclusive: new media can combine traditional folk dances, cultural dissemination and

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information exchange with information technology to rapidly spread traditional folk dances of Lingnan, providing easy access to this traditional form of culture through mobile terminals. They are also more inclusive than conventional dissemination channels like radio and TV. As for openness, new media provide an easier and less technically-demanding channel for production of videos of traditional folk dances of Lingnan, so everyone can be a receiver, a producer or a sharer of the dances. The major groups of users of new media are aged between 18 and 30, who are keen learners and find it easy to accept the short videos of traditional Lingnan dances. This means that new media users are increasingly young and diversified, leading to more competition in the media market. New media also feature diversity: there are various forms of information presentation of traditional folk dances of Lingnan. Information exchange of the traditional folk dances of Lingnan can be dynamic or static. Static dissemination involves spreading pictures, texts and other information of the dances; while dynamic dissemination refers to spreading videos and GIFs of the dances. The diverse ways of dissemination provided by new media can be opted as per the audience's actual conditions and preferences regardless of other factors. In other words, the diverse dissemination ways of new media dovetail with the young people's pursuit of personalized services in this modern world (Pu, Chen, Shi, Wang, 2020). As for timeliness, along with the rapid development of Internet and information technology, numerous Internet-based new-media platforms are springing up, which make it possible to let the audience know the time, venue, content of any event of traditional Lingnan dances once the information is released. On new media, the spatial or temporal limitations on dissemination of such information can be overcome and the dissemination efficiency is thereby increased.

General Conditions of Dissemination of Traditional Folk Dances of Lingnan

There are various traditional folk dances in the area to the south of the Five Ridges, including helou dance, qiangu dance, beihua dance, yingge dance, kylin dance, straw-dragon dance, spring-bull dance, dustpan dance, long-drum dance, bamboo-pole dance, shigong ritual dance, hunting-step dance, firewood dance and pingan dance. Some of them are dances of Cantonese, Chaozhou-Shantou, Hakka and other Han cultures around this area, and others are dances of Yao, Zhuang, She, Li and other ethnic minorities. These traditional folk dances, gradually formed by local people in their production practice and social life over the years, and passed down from generation to generation, boast vitality and distinctive local features. Given that the traditional folk dances have played an important role in the development of Lingnan culture, promoting these dances can help better understand the traditional folk dance cultures in this area, allow people to appreciate these dances, enjoy a visual feast of Lingnan culture and have a taste of more authentic experiences as participants, so that the audience can develop a higher emotional empathy and a better sense of national identity. On the whole, the traditional folk dances of Lingnan boast rich humanistic and artistic values, working to enhance the aesthetic judgment and critical thinking of viewers and players, and broaden their horizons. Therefore, in this new media era, we need to take into account of an integrated approach to dissemination, to help more young people, especially those in the big cities, to know these traditional folk dances better, thereby protecting this form of Lingnan culture from extinction.

The conventional modes of dissemination, mainly highlighting "Guangdong Music & Dance Festival for Mass", "Lingnan Dance Competition" and other professional and amateur dance events, have considerable spatial and temporal limitations. In addition, these folk events held around cities, county towns, townships and villages are of low profile and poor quality, which impede the dissemination and development of the folk dances. The rapid advancement of new media has diversified the ways of dissemination and allow the young people to watch videos of folk dances on networks anywhere anytime, free of previous spatial and temporal limitations (Dong, 2020). Meanwhile, relevant original presentations of traditional folk dances can also be delivered to young people through new media, allowing an opportunity for more young people to identify the cultural implications and artistic appeals of these traditional folk dances, to find their cultural identity in these dances. Furthermore, new media techniques like quick motion and slow motion, video editing and special effects processing can be applied to making videos for these folk dances in an integrated manner, which, together with bullet screen comments, help to draw together young people of the same interest from different

regions. This will encourage the young generation to imitate, disseminate and inherit these traditional folk dances.

Dissemination Channels for Traditional Folk Dances of Lingnan

Recreating Dissemination Channels and Expanding Communication Spaces

In these years, the blooming new media have completely helped re-create the dissemination channels for traditional folk dances of Lingnan, adding to instead of wiping out the previous ones. Efforts have been made to use short video social platforms and interactive video platforms to preserve the essences of the traditional folk dances of Lingnan, and make innovations in presentation modes and dissemination channels. At the same time, we are paying more attention to those young groups of favorable cultural attainment and artistic appreciation, guiding the younger generation to shoulder their responsibilities for promoting traditional culture and art, constantly extend the space and range for communication, and enhance the impact of the traditional folk dances of Lingnan.

Douyin Short Video Social Platform (“Douyin” for short), the Chinese version of Tik Tok, accommodates over 400 million active users of different ages and different education backgrounds. 40% of these users are aged from 24 to 30. Such a large base of audience helps capture mass flow and directional flow. The 2019 Douyin Data Report shows that it has become the largest platform for dissemination of knowledge, art and intangible cultural heritage around China in 2019, thanks to its advantageous platform. Short video platforms represented by Douyin have not only worked to promote content creation and establish an ecosystem for artistic creation in this new media era, but also shaped a brand-new ecosystem of knowledge. Chaoshan Yingge, originally a traditional folk dance peculiar to the Chaozhou-Shantou region, has been listed among the first batch of National Intangible Cultural Heritage, and usually performed around villages and urban fringe areas during spring festivals and other local festive occasions. In the eyes of the older generation in this region, Yingge represents a treasure of Chaoshan culture, emotionally bonding various people living there. Young natives in the urban area, however, have scarce knowledge of it, due to some spatial and temporal limitations. At Asia Arena 2019 Final, a dance regiment blended Chaoshan Yingge into their street dances and had impressive performance which spread around on Douyin and became a viral video posted on various new media video platforms. Many young people started to know its bold, solid, rough and unrestrained movements and postures, and its vast, mighty, strong and heroic imposing manners, making this dance a high-profile one in the minds of young people.

Integrating Dissemination Channels and Identifying Target Audience

Dance competitions, stage shows and folk events spreading only through conventional media channels cannot meet the demand of the younger generation for better knowledge of the traditional folk dances of Lingnan and their cultural values. In this new media era, young people under 30 years old are consuming information on various short video apps and interactive video platforms, checking on their cell phones more than 10 times on average per day, and sometimes at a rate of once every 10 minutes. It is even more noteworthy that these checks are made subconsciously rather than deliberately. In this new media era, an integrated approach to disseminating traditional folk dances of Lingnan using short video apps and interactive video platforms are encouraged. On the one hand, it allows the young audience to watch videos to appreciate these traditional folk dances at will anywhere anytime, and helps establish a library of these traditional folk dances. On the other hand, these platforms will see more diversified contents that add to content creation and social interaction, attract more young people who take interest in these folk dances, directly involve a large user base and encourage their viscosity and activeness.

A case in point could be the Bilibili Video Content Interactive Platform (Bilibili for short), a video platform and community that pools together young people of diversified cultural backgrounds. Its unique bullet-commenting function has helped gather numerous dance video creators and dance loving re-creators. They together work a wonder and build a synchronic bonding, a virtual tribe-like viewing atmosphere, making Bilibili a cultural community of interactive sharing and re-creation. Young people at different places in different time zones but with the same interest in the traditional

folk dances of Lingnan are drawn to this platform to have interactive communication and beyond. Free of spatial and temporal limitations, they spark up creative thoughts, so more and more young people are motivated to gather here, uploading, creating and re-creating more videos of the traditional folk dances of Lingnan.

In addition, We-Media represented by Weibo and WeChat Subscription Accounts, owned by private, general, wide-spread information disseminators, have also become very active channels for us to disseminate these traditional folk dances. Many older generation dancing artists, committed inheritors, researchers and lovers of the traditional folk dances of Lingnan, have signed up for their Weibo accounts, and some of them have even become “Big V” celebrities, great Internet influencers so to speak (Ai, Yu,2019). They work hard, digging deeper and exploring for channels to spread these traditional folk dances. Weibo, WeChat and other We-Media channels always timely launch some current hot topics in a proper manner, identifying good starting points to spread these dances, and unceasingly calling their audience to pay attention to these dances and get involved. Communication and interaction work a wonder in attracting followers, and we encourage more interactive involvements with the lovers of these traditional folk dances to make an effort together to spread the dances. Efforts are also made to build fan bases for the lovers of the traditional folk dances of Lingnan, maintain a good bonding with them, and unite them as an essential force to promote these dances. These fan bases may see a fission-like resonance, expanding the channels for spreading these dances unceasingly.

Building a Library of Resources and Realizing Diversified Development

Since the reform and opening-up, we have made a vigorous effort to revitalize our country and shift China from a traditional agricultural society to a modern industry one, but left our previous mainstream rural culture behind. The traditional folk dances of Lingnan, for example, having emerged and grown up in the rural area to the south of the Five Ridges, showcase the great wisdom of laboring people there. With Internet technology and internal information network architecture, we can connect the traditional folk dances of Lingnan to the Internet for better dissemination and overcome spatial and temporal barriers, so that the audience can watch and appreciate these dances freely and have communication with others at will. Shanghai Theatre Academy’s Museum of Traditional Chinese Opera, for example, has made it (Li, Zhang, 2018). In this way, the collection of resources can be presented to our audience in various modes, and they can search and inquire for relevant information free from spatial and temporal barriers. The information is utilized more extensively to accelerate dissemination of quality videos and promote these traditional folk dances. Technical measures like digitization, 3D image production and other computer technology can also be applied to collecting and processing the shows of these dances, build a library of data of these dances, and facilitate preservation and viewing. The 3D animation technology helps simulate real dances to make 3D cartoons of the traditional folk dances of Lingnan to better accommodate our targeted audience of the younger generation.

Conclusion

Cultural development, based on economic strength, is essential to economic advancement. To sum up, the traditional folk dances of Lingnan, as an indispensable component of Lingnan culture, duly represents the fine traditional Lingnan culture, and we need to keep the development of these traditional dances in line with the development of Lingnan culture to ensure their constant improvement. In this era of new media integration, we should find our ways to make use of short video platforms and interactive video platforms, build a library of data, and explore more channels to disseminate updated information of the traditional folk dances of Lingnan widely, so that the dances can be disseminated in a more targeted manner to develop and thrive, thereby achieving sustainable development.

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